

CHILDREN'S STORYBOOK DEVELOPMENT WITH LOCAL CULTURAL CHARACTERISTICS FOR HEALTHY LIVING BEHAVIOUR SUB THEME CURRICULUM 2013 CLASS V ELEMENTARY SCHOOL

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Abstract

This study aims to develop children's story books based on storybook components as well as the attitude and learning contents of the Healthy Lifestyle Curriculum subtheme 2013, as well as to know the effectiveness of storybooks. Development is done by entering a local culture that supports content itself. This research is continuing research result of design and product development using last three stages of ADDIE (Development, Implementation, and Evaluation). Subjects were 2 experts, 2 teachers of class V and 25 students. Data analysis method used descriptive qualitative. The result shows that, (1) the story book "Penyesalan Komang" contains spiritual attitudes (obedience of worship and gratitude and behavior), social attitude (honest, responsible, courteous, caring, confident), and the learning content of Bahasa Indonesia, PPKn, Mathematics, Science, Social Studies, SBDP and PJOK and there are supporting local cultures such as Mebanten Canang and Mebanten Saiban. Based on the results of the assessment of experts, obtained the quality and appropriateness of the story book "Penyesalan Komang" is very good. (2) Through the experiment, the effectiveness of the use of story books on the attitude of students is 13,72; of student reading interest 2,61; and student learning outcomes of 4.59 with a very effective category as a companion textbook curriculum 2013

Keywords: Story Book, Learning Content, Local Culture, Effectiveness.

INTRODUCTION

The progress of science and technology, which is accompanied by the influence of globalization, has had its own impact on the world of education. Education may not be able to relate the process of globalization that will create this global society. Changes that occur globally cause lifestyle changes in Indonesian society in general. The most effective way to deal with the era of globalization is through improving the quality of education. Muhibbin (in Hairida, 2011) said that education is basically a conscious effort to develop the potential of students' human resources by encouraging and facilitating their learning activities. This opinion provides an understanding that quality education is not only developing the intelligence of students, but also developing all the potential they have, so that they are able to compete in a global society.

The definition of education by Ki Hajar Dewantara implies that through education, it should be realized with the perfection of the lives of students through various forms of intelligence,

whether spiritual, emotional, social and intellectual. This intelligence is very important for students to have in order to improve the quality of education in the global era. Gunamantha (2010) also added that education is fundamental to achieving sustainable goals. The implementation of the 2013 curriculum in elementary schools uses the main characteristics of integrated thematic learning. Integrated thematic learning is learning that is designed based on themes to link several subjects, so that it can provide meaningful experiences to students. Thematic learning is an effort to integrate knowledge in a comprehensive and integrated manner, developing student understanding so that students will be more involved in learning activities. Through a network of themes, students can connect ideas with experiences and the environment in which students live. Realizing the importance of being integrated in meeting the learning needs of the 21st century and preparing students to develop higher order thinking skills that will later be needed in an increasingly globalized world (Davies, 2011). Students must also learn essential skills for success in today's world, such as critical thinking, problem solving, communication and collaboration (Partnership for 21st Century Skills, 2009). Thus, thematic learning allows students to develop higher order thinking skills.

Based on the above, the challenges faced by education do not only come from the education system internally, even more are external challenges or challenges that come from outside the education system itself. External challenges from the education system should be the main source of aspirations in making changes and updating the education system internally. Thus, education will not continue to be accused of building its own island as well as the criticisms that are always thrown from various parties who pay attention to the national education system. The future challenge for the education system in Indonesia is not only about how to improve the quality and efficiency of education internally (internal efficiency), but even more important is how to improve the compatibility of education with other areas of life (external efficiency). The development of the education system should not only be aimed at the development of education as a separate system, but also the development of the education system as one system or an integral part of another wider system. Thus the development of the education system must be able to provide functional meaning for national development in various fields of community life. Given the importance of improving the quality of education, the government considers it necessary to create a legal umbrella, namely the National Education System. In RI Law No. 20 of 2003, Article 3 of the UUSPN explains that "National education functions to develop capabilities and shape the character and civilization of a dignified nation in the context of educating the nation's life, aiming to develop the potential of students to become human beings who believe and fear God Almighty, have character noble, healthy, knowledgeable, capable, creative, independent, and become a democratic and responsible citizen. Article 1 of the Law also explains that education is "a conscious and planned effort to create a learning atmosphere and learning process so that students actively develop their potential to have religious spiritual strength, self-control, personality, intelligence, noble character, and the skills they need. , society, nation and state" (Depdiknas, 2003:3).

The formulation of the national education goals reflects the general picture of the Indonesian human figure that is expected and must be produced through the implementation of every educational program. Therefore, the formulation of national education goals becomes the basis

for developing the cultural values of the nation's character in schools based on Pancasila, the 1945 Constitution and the culture of the Indonesian nation. One form of successful implementation of the 2013 curriculum at the elementary school level is literacy skills, one of which is reading literacy for elementary school students. Reading literacy is not enough if it is only honed at school but also needs to be done at home. The way that can be done to attract students' interest in reading literacy is to create a fun learning environment such as providing picture story books which of course can attract students' interest to see and begin to develop a desire to read. The ability to read is the most basic ability that must be mastered by children from an early age, especially at the elementary school (SD) level because this is where the formation of children's language skills begins. From the availability of textbooks in schools, students are expected to be motivated to read. In addition to textbooks, other companion books are also needed to add to the attractiveness of students.

Cultivating a reading culture is very important, especially for the younger generation who are the spearhead of the life of the nation and state. In learning to read, the most important thing is how to foster a desire in students to read and improve their reading comprehension. The more students read often, the higher the level of reading ability. Marhaeni (2015) said that through reading, information and knowledge that is useful for life can be obtained. This is the main motivation that can encourage the growth and development of interest in reading. If the child already has a high level of understanding in reading, it will be easier for the child to learn his lessons at school. Often children feel bored when reading textbooks for that we also have to look for other alternatives, which can be interesting, for example by using story books based on learning content.

The storybook is packed with elements of learning content and local culture. Because every child likes stories and stories that are in accordance with the culture where students live, it can make it easier for students to recognize and understand stories. In addition, story books are also relatively cheap and easy to find. In the implementation of the 2013 curriculum, character education can be integrated into all learning in every field of study contained in the curriculum. Learning materials related to norms or values in each field of study need to be developed, made explicit, connected to the context of everyday life. Value education and character building are not only carried out at the cognitive level, but touch internalization, and real experiences in everyday life. In general, character education emphasizes exemplary, environmental creation, and habituation, through various scientific tasks and conducive activities. So that what students see, hear, feel and do can shape their character. In addition to making exemplary and habituation the main educational method, the creation of a climate and culture as well as a conducive environment is also very important, and helps shape the character of students. The use of story books in this learning is expected to be a tool to achieve the goals that have been set.

Meanwhile, based on research conducted by Marhaeni, et al (2013) it was found that the 2013 curriculum textbooks for elementary school students were still more expository-oriented. Elementary school children mostly have characteristics that are narrative rather than expository. Expository is a logical explanation or description. While the narrative is a series of

sentences that are narrative or descriptive. In addition, the 2013 curriculum textbooks also still use non-local cultural contexts so that this causes the meaning of learning to be not optimal.

Regardless of the efforts conducted to prepare the curriculum and textbooks, it has been found that there is another side that may interfere with the successful implementation of the 2013 curriculum. It is assumed that if the learning in the classroom is expository oriented, then there is a possibility of student boredom in learning. Characteristically, students prefer a narrative or storytelling approach. If that happens, the delivery of the material will not go well. Based on that assumption, it is also very important to have complementary materials such as textbooks that are narrative in nature, namely in the form of story books.

So far, there have been no studies that directly address this weakness. However, research by Marhaeni, et al (2016) has also produced a prototype story book as a companion to textbooks that contains story content in the form of learning content from themes and subthemes and uses local Balinese culture that is relevant to these subthemes. Guidelines for local wisdom values are the criteria that determine the quality of children's actions because Suastra (2017) says local wisdom is defined as truth that has become a tradition. Character education in students is important to instill the values of local wisdom. Because basically local wisdom is a truth that has become a tradition or is permanent in an area. Local wisdom is a combination of religious values and various existing goodness values. Local wisdom is formed as a cultural advantage of the local community and geographical conditions in a broad sense.

Therefore, the prototype is only limited to the contents of the storybook, while the contents of the storybook are generated from the results of an analysis of the lesson content on the themes of low-grade textbooks. Thus it is said that the prototype already provides story books for each theme in the high grade. More specifically, Kharisma (2017) developed a prototype storybook for the theme Healthy Is Important. This prototype must be developed into a story book to be used in learning the sub-theme of Healthy Lifestyle. So far, there has been no study that directly discusses the research by Marhaeni, et al (2016) using the ADDIE model (Analysis, Design, Development, Implementation, Evaluation). However, the research has just completed the Analysis and Design stage with the result in the form of a children's story book prototype. While the stages of Development, Implementation, and Evaluation will be carried out in this research. The three stages aim to develop a prototype into a storybook, test the results of the storybook to fifth grade elementary school children, and test the effectiveness of the storybook.

Based on this description, researchers are interested in studying further about the development of children's story books as learning media to assist teachers in packaging learning into more interesting learning. In addition, in story books, researchers can also insert character values that are integrated with local culture in it, therefore the researchers made a story book on the subtheme "Healthy Lifestyle" for fifth grade elementary school students.

METHODS

This type of research is design and product development research (Design and Development) using the ADDIE Model (Analysis, Design, Development, Implementation, Evaluation). Hall

(2006) says Research and Development (R&D) is a term commonly used to describe activities undertaken by companies and other entities such as individual entrepreneurs to create product and process improvements. Richey and Klein (2005) say there are two categories of development research, one of which is development studies that focus on a given product, program, process, or tool. Usually this development study does not only discuss product design and development, but also evaluation. So the research and development method is to produce products that can later be tested for effectiveness. So the research and development method is to produce products that can later be tested for effectiveness. This research was conducted at SD Negeri 1 Dajan Peken which is located at Jalan Diponegoro Number 19 Tabanan, Bali Province. This elementary school consists of 23 classes, each class consisting of ± 25 students. SD Negeri 1 Dajan Peken has an A accreditation and is the first public elementary school to become a Piloting Project for the implementation of the 2013 Curriculum in Tabanan Regency. The class used in the study was class V A with a total of 25 students. The research was conducted on April 16-21, 2018.

The stages of this research, namely the Analysis and Design stage, have been carried out in previous research, namely the research of Kharisma (2017) on the analysis of attitudes and learning content on the Healthy Is Important theme in the 2013 5th grade elementary school curriculum. While the stages of this research are Development, Implementation, and Evaluation. The development stage is the stage of the process of making storybooks, while the implementation stage is the stage of applying the results of the storybooks to fifth grade elementary school students and the last stage, namely Evaluation, is to test the effectiveness of using the children's storybooks. The research subjects are the parties that are used as samples in a study. The role of the subject is to provide responses and information related to the data needed by researchers and provide input to researchers, either directly or indirectly.

The subjects in the study were 2 practitioners and 2 experts. The variables in this study are: (1) the values of spiritual attitudes, (2) social attitudes, (3) aspects of learning content, (4) local culture in the lives of high school students and (5) the effectiveness of using story books.

The spiritual attitude in the study refers to the KI-1 Curriculum 2013 which is to accept, practice and respect the teachings of the religion they adhere to, with indicators that include: (a) obedience to worship and (b) behaving in gratitude. The social attitudes in this study are (honest, responsible, polite, caring, confident). Local culture in this study is Balinese cultural values that are closely related to the lives of elementary school children, namely saying greetings in question is local cultural greetings, and the obligation to pray in local culture is called mebantén.

The data in this study were the results of a questionnaire on the quality of story books by experts/culturalists, the results of the assessment of the quality of story books by teachers of students' reading interest, the results of the observation sheets of spiritual and social attitudes and the scores of the student learning outcomes tests. Data analysis carried out in this study used a qualitative descriptive analysis method. Qualitative descriptive analysis is research that is obtained based on the meaning of research findings, research results are obtained from the relationship to research subjects, observations, document records, then data is obtained from

words that have been described, and interpreted. This is in accordance with the opinion of Agung (2005:60) stating, "the method of qualitative descriptive analysis is a way of processing data by systematically arranging in sentences, words, categories about an object". Then Sanjaya (2014: 47) argues, "descriptive qualitative analysis method is a research method that aims to describe in full and in depth about social reality, phenomena that exist in the community that are the subject of research so that the characteristics, characters, traits, models of the phenomenon are described" . So the qualitative descriptive analysis method is a method that is made systematically in descriptive form in the form of words, sentences, categories of objects that occur in social reality and phenomena in society.

This method is used to determine the results of the effectiveness of story books, namely reading interest, attitudes, and learning outcomes, after using children's story books as a companion to K-13 textbooks with the subtheme Healthy Lifestyle for fifth grade elementary school students. The results of the two questionnaires were analyzed using the T-test formula. The results of the analysis of all student questionnaires showed how much effectiveness the use of story books as a companion to K-13 textbooks was. After knowing the effectiveness of story books, it will be continued by testing the learning outcomes that follow learning with student learning outcomes who are taught with the help of story books and student learning outcomes that are not taught with the help of story books.

The formula for the amount of effectiveness used is as follows.

$$M = \frac{\sum x}{N}$$

(Sudijono, 2011:82)

Information; M= Sample average; x= Sum of values; N= The number of subjects involved/individuals who are the sample.

$$u = \frac{0,65 \times SMI}{N}$$

(Bruning,1997)

Information;

u = The population average determined/referring to the minimum KKM;

SMI = Ideal Maximum Standard;

N = The number of subjects involved/individuals who were sampled.

$$t = \frac{M - u}{\sqrt{\frac{\sum x^2 - \frac{(\sum x)^2}{N}}{N(N-1)}}$$

(Bruning, 1997)

Information;

t = Koefisien t-test;

M = Sample average;

\mathcal{U} = The population average is determined / refers to the minimum KKM;

Σx^2 = The sum of the squared scores; $(\Sigma x)^2$ = Square of the total score;

N = The number of subjects involved/individuals who were sampled.

$$ES = t \sqrt{\frac{1}{N}}$$

(Bruning, 1997)

Information;

ES= Purity effectiveness, t = Coefficient t -test; N= The number of subjects involved/individuals who were sampled.

After calculating, then categorized based on the effectiveness table as follows.

Table 1. Purity Effectiveness (ES)

Efek Size (ES)	Information
$ES < 0,2$	Less effective
$0,2 < ES < 0,8$	Effective
$0,8 < ES$	Very effective

The test criteria H_0 is rejected if tcount ttable with a significance level of 5% with $db = n_1 + n_2 - 2$. This means that if there is an average difference between before and after using story books as a companion to different textbooks, it can be said that there is an effect of using story books on learning outcomes for fifth grade elementary school on the sub-theme of Healthy Lifestyle.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This research is a continuation of previous research using the ADDIE (Analysis, Design, Development, Implementation, Evaluation) model. The Analysis and Design stages have been carried out in previous studies, while the Development, Implementation, and Evaluation stages were carried out in this study. The following is a description of the stages of Development, Implementation, and Evaluation in the following table

Table 2: Children's Storybook Development Model

No	Development Stage	Results
1.	Development	In the form of a story book for children in grade 5 elementary school with the theme Healthy Lifestyle, the sub-theme Healthy Is Important, which has gone through the stages of preparing a story framework, making sketches and coloring pictures by illustrators, and assessing the quality of the storybooks. The quality assessment of story books was carried out by 2 elementary school teachers and 2 experts. The final result of this stage is a children's story book with the title "Kolang Regret"
2.	Implementation	The use of the story book "Penyesal Kolang" in the fifth grade of State Elementary School 1 Dajan Peken, Tabanan is as a companion book for textbooks. At this stage a teacher learning scenario is made. The results of this stage are data and documentation of the implementation of learning by using story books as companion books.
3.	Evaluation	Testing the results of the implementation of learning by using story books to determine the effectiveness of the story books. The test was carried out using the formula from James L. Burning.1997. The result of this stage is that the story book "Penyesal Kolang" is effectively used as a companion to the textbook.

The results of the research in the form of questionnaire data for assessing the quality of story books were judged by 2 experts, namely Undiksha Fine Arts expert lecturer (Drs. IGN. Widnyana, M.Erg) and Undiksha Postgraduate Basic Education expert lecturer Prof. Dr. A.A.I.N Marhaeni, MA. The storybook suitability questionnaire answered by the expert about the quality of children's storybooks on the sub-theme of Healthy Living found that the mean observation value was 96. If the mean value was compared in the PAIT category table, then the value was in the very good category.

The storybook quality assessment questionnaire was judged by 2 teachers at SDN 1 Dajan Peken, namely Loris Sinambela, S.Pd., M.Pd as homeroom teacher for class V A and Ni Putu Piki Pia Arini, S.Pd.SD as homeroom teacher for class V B. it was obtained that the mean value of observations was 68. If the mean value was compared in the PAIT category table, then the value was in the very good category. The results of the analysis of the effectiveness of storybooks in terms of students' attitudes indicate that these storybooks are very effective in improving students' spiritual attitudes and social attitudes in their daily behavior. In accordance

with the opinion of Adipta, et al (2016) stated, Grades 4-5 students prefer stories related to everyday life or stories that reflect experiences similar to those experienced by students, the stories presented are also more complex. So story books about everyday experiences can provide good behavior for students' attitudes both spiritually and socially. The effectiveness of the attitude is 13.72 which states Very Effective.

The spiritual attitudes that can be seen based on the findings in the story books are 1) students increase their gratitude by diligently worshiping according to their respective religions; and 2) students improve their worship obedience by knowing when it is time to pray together. The social attitudes that can be seen based on the findings are 1) being honest in doing assignments without cheating, it can be seen that students do assignments and learning outcomes well, are not noisy and no one cheats; 2) responsibility by doing the tasks assigned and collected on time; 3) polite by dressing quickly and cleanly; 4) caring for friends by sharing paper when working on problems; 5) confident that many students dare to appear in front of the class to answer and practice baseball playing activities.

The results of the analysis of the effectiveness of story books in terms of students' reading interest indicate that this storybook is very effective in increasing students' reading interest both in the dimensions of feeling happy, focusing attention, using time, motivation to read, and effort to read. So, such as encouragement, motivation, attention, given by people closest to students such as: teachers, family, environment can influence and increase students' reading interest. All of these dimensions can be seen from the changes in students who ask to be read again the story book "toga savior" and other story books. It was also seen that they were enthusiastic about bringing the story books they had at home to exchange story books and some of them also went to the library to read story books. A well-managed library can make it easier for students to get books, one of which is the desired story book (Triatma, 2016). The effectiveness of reading interest is 2.61 which states Very Effective.

The results of the analysis of the effectiveness of story books in terms of student learning outcomes show that this storybook is very effective in improving student learning outcomes, it can be seen that the value of 10 multiple choice questions can be answered well by students. Learning outcomes include Indonesian, Mathematics, PPKn, Science, Social Studies, PJOK, and SBdP subjects. The effectiveness of learning outcomes is 4.59 which states Very Effective.

Based on the results of the analysis of the three aspects, namely reading interest, learning outcomes and observational assessments of students' social and spiritual attitudes, the most prominent is the effectiveness in the field of attitudes. Research by Retnowati, G., Salim, R. M. A., & Saleh, A. Y (2018) entitled Effectiveness of picture story books reading to increase kindness in children aged 5-6 years also proves that picture story books have an impact on increasing positive behavior in children. through a study involving 31 children aged 5-6 years; they were taken from a kindergarten in Bandung as participants. The study was conducted by children by reading eight picture books for eight days. There is also a study by Olfah,, Mendri N.K, and Palestin B in the Journal of Health showing the results that there is an effect of using story books about attitudes and behaviors that care about the cleanliness of the school environment on the attitude of caring about the cleanliness of the school environment. The

same thing was also expressed by Crippen (2012) in his research entitled *The Value of Children's Literature* published in *Oneota Reading Journal* that children's story books play an important role because they give students the opportunity to respond to a reading; provide opportunities to appreciate more about their own cultural heritage and that of others; helping students develop emotional intelligence and creativity; and maintain the growth and development of students' personality and social skills;

With the support of several relevant research results, it can be concluded that the children's story book entitled "Penyesal Komang" has proven to have an effect on students' attitudes such as being more active in carrying out prayers before and after starting activities at school. Students are also more motivated not to forget to give canang saris every day in the classroom because and a caring attitude through mutual cooperation in carrying out picket assignments, all these behaviors are accommodated in story books through the behavior shown by Komang is worthy of emulation and is very in line with the real situation. what children do every day

CONCLUSION

As for what can be concluded from this research that this storybook was created and developed with several aspects, namely a) spiritual attitude, namely obedience to worship which is manifested by obediently carrying out Tri Sandhya which is lifted from the local Balinese culture of Satua Timun Mas, and behaving in gratitude with mebanten canang prayer activities. sari; b) social attitudes that are honest, responsible, polite, caring, and confident which are manifested by several local Balinese cultural activities for high-grade elementary school students, namely: this story book has the meaning of several satua stories (Ramayana, Kebo Iwa, Timun Mas, Cupak Grantang), traditional tug of war game, Pupuh Pucung song, greetings from Om Swastyastu and Om Santhi Santhi Santhi Om; and 3) learning content such as: Civics on rights and obligations, Indonesian on obtaining information from reading texts, Mathematics on floor plans, Science on a healthy environment, Social Studies on the rights and obligations of family members, SBDP on dance, and PJOK on playing small ball or ball. baseball sport. These three aspects can be packaged in making a good storybook, namely a) opening the story, so that readers are interested in reading; b) leads to preoccupation; c) the middle of the story, so as not to be boring; d) climax, there is a distinct impression; and e) draw the meaning of the story, so that the meaning conveyed can reach the reader. Based on the results of attitude observation sheets, reading interest questionnaires, and learning outcomes tests, it can be concluded that the children's story book entitled "Penyesal Komang" is very effectively used as a companion book for learning books in the 2013 Curriculum with the sub-theme Healthy Lifestyle used in the learning process in class V. Elementary school, because students experience changes for the better in spiritual and social attitudes, reading interest, and learning outcomes. Based on the conclusions and implications of the research that has been described previously, there are several suggestions that can be used to improve the quality of learning in applying K-13 to elementary students, among others, students are advised to further improve their spiritual and social attitudes, reading interest, learning outcomes, towards a better direction. either by utilizing companion books, one of which is children's story books with local cultural nuances with various learning content. Teachers are advised to be able to improve and

provide creative ideas, especially for making children's story books as a companion to textbooks in K-13. It is suggested that schools can help schools to provide knowledge for teachers to be able to use effectively the children's story books that have been made, so that in the future schools can make students with better behavior. As well as for other researchers, it is recommended to carry out further research to improve children's story books, so that they can create children's story books that can function as learning formulas on themes in high grade.

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